

Appendix: Full TABLE OF Themes, Subthemes, and Quotes

Theme	Subtheme	Quotes
1. Adoption of public reporting system in Finland	Need for adoption	<p><i>“Yes, Finland needs. But we must as I earlier said we must develop these reporting systems. So that they focus more and more to quality and effectiveness of healthcare. (P4)”</i></p>
		<p><i>Well, that's also a question of... We have been very organization-centered here. We have built an organization or organizations that come along quite well without any patients. And now we have to be, in this social reform, we have to be patient-centered. We have to do these things for the patient more openly. And I think, yes, we do. (P6)</i></p>
		<p><i>No, work for it should be begin now. But of course, when it's done well, if you compare it, for example, to kanta or the electronic prescription, many feel that those were done a bit hastily or the result wasn't as good. (P11)</i></p>
Applicability		<p><i>Yeah, of course it would be. I think it would be applicable all over the world. But coming back to what I said just a minute ago about, let's say, elective surgeries, there are areas of healthcare that you can have sort of reliable comparative statistics. (P2)</i></p>
		<p><i>Well, I personally don't see any obstacles. So, it could be. It could be.</i></p> <p><i>In my opinion, I mean, it's only a matter of data and it's a matter of how you can... Is there uses for that? (P1)</i></p>
		<p><i>Applicable? Yeah. Yes, sure.</i></p>

I mean, they tried it previously with the Finland's social and healthcare reform, the last government. I don't know what they're doing at the moment. They used to, they had this Social and HealthCare Data Package thingy where they would have organized healthcare. Because the Kokoomus was in charge of the last government. They had this Social and Health Care Data Package thing that they could then use the data and compare private and public.
(P13)

Partially, yes, because, for instance, university hospitals have collaborated for a long time to provide comparable information about the quality and accessibility of the services. Not everyone publishes it in the same way, but we use the same indicators. And part of this information is obligatory for us because the government requires us to report, for instance, care accessibility, waiting times for different services every three months. (P9)

2. Content of public reporting systems in Finland

Quality

About this system, reporting systems. What is the challenge of our systems? So that we get more. We can develop the system so that there is more knowledge of quality. What is the quality? Before that we must think how we get knowledge of quality. What are the indicators of quality?
(P4)

Then, absolutely most importantly, their success rate, meaning complications, infections, readmissions, and that sort of thing. So, the quality issue. (P2)

Of course, anything that the law requires. Access to care, quality of care, the amount of

personnel, the quality of personnel, costs and financing. (P9)

Waiting times

Well, how long do you have to wait to get to doctor's diagnosis appointment? I think that's that's what most of the people want to see. (P6)

Well, of course, the queues are a matter of discussion. So how long have you been waiting before you get treatment? So that's absolutely something that should be public. (P11)

Availability of health services information

You would want to have that sort of customer satisfaction measurement. If I would be, say, a government regulator, yeah, if I'd be in the Ministry of Health, then I would also want to have data about all these things, plus capacity utilization rate, staffing levels, and the quality, production cost, that sort of thing. Because then my job would be to watch over the taxpayers' money. So, I would want all the relevant information about how taxpayers' money is spent.

We need to give out the information of, first of all, effectiveness. So how well can we answer to the demand of the needs people have. (P2)

So do they, when they try to contact us, do they get through, do they get the assessment of the need of treatment they need, do they get to the treatment when they need it, what are the times that this goes on. And after that, we should have better information of the effectiveness of this process. It is harder to find out how to measure it, but that is the effectiveness of treatment and also the quality, so that there are no failures of treatment, so to call.

And also, when we talk about the government or our administration, we need the information of the use of resources and how effective are these hospitals, how many patients can they take, how many operations can they do compared to the others. So that when we know what is going on, we can see is there something that we need to do better, that kind of things.
(P3)

3. Challenges of introducing public reporting systems into the Finnish healthcare system.

Political Climate

The political impact is much, has much more influence than it used to have. I think that the public healthcare system was more independent, more independently governed by the municipalities, and now with the new political system with number of wellbeing and services counties, the government and the ministries have taken much more, much more attempts to guide the system. (P9)

Well, I guess it is a political question in the end if this is implemented or not. And well, if you're talking right now, it is the right-wing parties that are in the lead in the country. Well, I don't know. Could they be more interested in the system? Maybe, because at least before they were in favor of more freedom to choose. I guess they are still. So, I guess there would be political approval for this kind of a system right now, well, compared to the last government at least. (P12)

Yeah, well, the impact is fairly large, and since the last government, they had an agenda and legislation and guidelines about what the public reporting should be, the work was a bit more focused now this government, they don't, they

dropped all of it, so they still issued money to the well-being counties, and they can still use it to produce these reporting systems. But there's it there's less sort of guidelines, less direction from, from like direct government. So that's why the efforts are sort of more spread out at the moment. I mean, from our perspective, our clients. (P13)

Professional resistance

Absolutely. It will be. I'm sure that it will be a problem and there will be resistance. Because, for example, in my career, I have been doing this kind of development projects in healthcare for almost two decades. And no matter if it's a small change, the doctors will resist. If it's a big change, they will resist even more.

And now we are talking about a very big change in what affects their profession. So there will be resistance. (P8)

Well, this brings us to the question of professions, professionals, who as a collective become a profession, the medical community, the profession of doctors and then all the specialties. So, there's a big sociological literature on professions. And if you're part of a profession, you are loyal to the profession where you're supposed to be.

If the profession determines that they don't want to have this kind of information out there, then that would be a big complication. (P2)

I don't think that because I have experience on very, very enthusiastic clinicians working to develop a quality system to prove that our quality is good or if we have some fault in our quality. And we have done this for about 20 years only based on the enthusiasm from the clinicians and from the hospitals itself. The government was not interested in supporting this quality reporting system. It was the clinicians and their organizations now, a couple of years ago, THL again, has started to develop national quality systems, where, of course, the clinicians are major collaborators, because they are the only one who can interpret the data, researchers and clinicians. (P9)

Well, there might be some more for some more again, but I think majority would be for public reporting. Well, I think it would be providing a valuable tool for the doctors as well, because if something gets reported publicly, if something it reveals things that are not done well, and will, of course, provide an incentive for the counties, for the hospitals, to improve on those things that are not done well. Because we of course, want to be treating our patients optimally with as good as possible results, and we also want to have the tools to monitor those results. So, it's a shared interest with the public and the doctors to provide as good care as possible, and that might give an incentive for those who, for example, control the resources that somewhere more resources might be needed to achieve a better outcome. (P11)

Resource constraints

Money makes the world go round. At the moment, we are struggling in in a way that we have never experienced with the lack of funding

for our basic activities. We are behind our funding on the public social healthcare, 1.4 billion euros. So, we try to find all means to show the Ministry of Economics that we are already working in very economical way, we are doing our utmost to improve our performance, to save resources. If it's medicines or stuff or instruments or anything that we don't cause extra costs but, but the gap is so huge that we can think of improving anything that would in the way that would increase costs. That's the mode at the moment and will be for some years.

(P9)

It's coming from the political system because the welfare regions are supposed to be independent in providing the services and producing the services, but they are not independent in their funding, but they get their funding from the state and the state's funding that was calculated based on a model was, well, it just turned out that the funding wasn't sufficient because when the municipalities were in charge of the health care, it was split in the municipality's budget in a way that wasn't, it wasn't just possible to make a one to one transfer of this part of the budget to the welfare regions. And now, since all of the welfare regions are running under the budget, they are, of course, turning back to the state to provide them with more funding and that's a political decision whether or not to provide that. And so far, the answer has been no.

(P11)

And then we don't have resources for making user-friendly, you know, applications where it's easy to find that kind of information. So, we are not sort of hiding it, but we are not making it

that easy either. And the same is, for example, in Kela (Social Insurance Institution of Finland). Kela has its own tietotarjotin (Data platform). And it's also, you know, lots and lots of information. If you just find it, you'll find lots of information. But these kind of government institutions don't have the funding to, and of course don't have the knowledge to do them that user-friendly. And if you go to Statistics Finland, there are different kinds of registers. For example, lots of mortality information, causes of death. (P5)

4. Information system challenges Data

The first part where it is, how do nurses and doctors write down the data? Is it accurate what they write down when they see a patient? What happens there?

What kind of appointments, what kind of symptom, what kind of treatment we have made that we always write it down the same way so that we can know that the basic data is, we are talking about the same thing all the time. That is the main point. And we still have some development to be done in that department. And there is that we still have a lot of different systems where we gather the data from.(P3)

Well, we haven't been able to get consistent data from the things we do THL for example, we have now in Varha (Wellbeing services county of Southwest Finland) , here, here in Southeast, southwestern Finland, we have still some 30, 40, what is called the computer databases, yeah, databases and we are, we have been buying some, introducing, some, some new, new databases that are based on patient, patient and client data, so that everybody in Varha gets through one computer program, but it takes

time. The data that we get is not homogenous, not yet. We will have to do some things in order to get the information in a similar manner from these data sources. (P6)

I think that the major issue is that the data is not up to date, so there are quite a long time periods. The data might be updated once a year or twice a year, so it's kind of old data when you use it.

And also, another major issue is that these public reporting systems, all the measures that there are, they are calculated to that kind of a high level, so sometimes there might be some thoughts that the data is not valid, but we cannot validate it, so that's another issue. (P8)

Well, we have a lot to do with data management and the lack of funding for systems for making information from that data is a hinder. Because when we have been waiting for this reform, we have not invested in reporting systems because we believe that the government will make us use certain tools that are chosen by the government. So why invest money on something that would not be available or we cannot use it after some years? It requires a lot of work to make data to information and knowledge. It is not simple. (P9)

Regulations

Patient records is a very sensitive kind of information. So, you certainly know in Finland

that the patient data is protected by layers and layers of administrative rules that we want to do research on health service production. It's very difficult to get access to data. (P2)

But it has always been about regulation. I mean, like the technical limits are nothing. It has always been about regulation. And again, when you talk about regulation, then the regulation dictates that somebody has to organize and then somebody has to produce. And it's been a sort of different, there have been different organizations. (P13)

Legislation is quite tight on the privacy of healthcare data, so you have to run a quite strict shop when handling, of course it's sensitive data, sensitive health information of the people, but the legislation is very, very strict so it might even hamper the effective use of data because you need to get all sorts of permissions and licenses to actually use the data for anything useful and currently, for example, making any use of the data for research purposes is quite difficult and a complicated and expensive. (P11)

Well, there's this problem that has arisen at least with new laws implemented in Finland regarding data safety a few years ago, maybe three years ago, with the GDPR.

That also, but it's related to a local law that made it quite hard to make at least medical research in Finland. At least many scientists, medical professional researchers have complained about it. So that's one thing that I think is quite generally accepted that it was a bit of a mistake to make the data safety laws so strict that it actually restricts making research. At least in medical field. So I guess, and I hope, changes are coming to that law in a few years. And it might, well, I don't know if it's related to this system.

But of course, the EU GDPR system has its limits also. And data safety is a double-edged sword that, of course, there needs to be restricted access, but it can't. The problem is that if people can't do their work and research because of it, it causes problems. (P12)

How deep you can go and how deep you should go if you want to have comparable data for the consumers. So that may be a problem because these GDPR problems are always there. Particularly here in Finland, it's quite an issue. (P1)
